

General Hari Seldon Private Commission Permanent Resolution Act: Parbatya Commonwealth Act for Independence of Autonomy Government, Formation of Legislative Assembly House and Parliament Building Construction

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Abstract

Along with the major organ of the doctrinal operations, the Permanent Resolution Act, this research presented a situation review article on the Doctrine of the Chittagong Peace Process in Bangladesh with few global strikeable issues. Unarmed surviving Parbatya Chittagong nation of Buddhists population in Bangladesh has not yet been able to form their government since 1997 to 2023, so it has been assumed that Prime Minister Sheikh Hasina & Awami League Government of Bangladesh (ALGOB) cheated to weaponless freedom fighters Buddhists people by taking their weapons through the Chittagong Hill Tracts Peace Accord 1997 that was signed between Bangladesh and Chittagong Hill Tracts in order to a Commonwealth of Independence of Autonomy Government, Formation of Legislative Assembly House and Parliament Building Construction, which is also the last official initiative of the Parbatya Peace Process in the Chinese Belt and Road. Following the theater of war between the US-led NATO—Ukraine alliance and the Russian Federation, the 3rd World War situations intended to expand between Bangladesh and Myanmar. This doctrinal paper has been presented through codification of situations of the post-seizure war-fighting battles surviving cold and silent conflicts in Parbatya, Chittagong Hill Tracts, in order to deliver the seized nation onto a free pathway.

Keywords: Kingdom of Parbatya Commonwealth, Religion of Buddhism, Chittagong Hill Tracts Peace Accord, Permanent Resolution Act, Bangladesh, United States Democracy Vision, Human Rights and Peace, Situation Review, Doctrinal Paper.

Introduction

President Xi Jinping is working to activate the Chinese Belt and Road Nations' One Initiative (BRI). Whereas Bangladesh is also a member state of the Belt & Road and as well neighboring country Bharat which is also called as "India" in English society since England's Indias historical cultures were exported to the Hindustan Mahabharat Bers and Americas & the Caribbean, is one member too. Bangladesh and Bharat are also member nations of the English Commonwealth of Nations. The English King of the United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland (UK) Charles III is a Monarch to Australia, Canada, and many Commonwealth states and territories/regions. King Charles III is also head of the Commonwealth of Nations. Therefore, their British rules and interests may come first, as well as British laws also available in Bangladesh, since the British Empire ruled this Great Bharat Belt.

Discussion

Chittagong Hill-Tracts Peace Process is still surviving in Bangladesh for many decades whereas Buddhist majority people were fighting for their freedom & rights. Throughout the process, the Chittagong Hill Tracts Peace Accord was signed in 1997 between the Bangladesh Government and Parbatya CHT Freedom Fighters Forces in order to provide them independence of the region in autonomous status by allowing them to make Chittagong Hill-Tracts Regional Government and to recognize their nation's identity; also deployed Bangladesh Military Forces active duties, reserves, volunteers, civilian manpowers, military camps, bases, and establishments should be withdrawn from the entire Parbatya state. Currently, the Buddhists' majority population is known as indigenous, tribal, and small and micro nations, and many tribes have their own languages and their religious beliefs are Buddhism, which is herein the local faith of the majority, culture, and religious practices, and the population is also very local. However, the foreign faith and culture/practice of Arabian hegemonism Islamized in Bangladesh under another foreign faith Christism leadership. Thus, the local believers in Hinduism and Buddhism were eliminated by more than 90% and have been identified as a minor population group.

Bangladesh is now an Islamic state where most of the population is Muslim and government and private fields everywhere

the Muslimism prioritizes. In addition, rules under the Christism leadership of the United Kingdom Commonwealth of Nations, the most recently inaugurated King Charles III, is headed to all member states, including Bangladesh, and directly monarch King to the many member states and territories/regions in the world. Thus, religiously discriminated Buddhists people did not address ever in Bangladesh in the rightful ways, and the Chittagong Peace Process' last signed official agreement to allow Hill-Tracts majority people Buddhism believers to build their own government form and Bangladesh armies withdraw—still did not execute. However, Bangladesh has increased the number of Muslims by millions, which is another step to completely eliminate the Buddhist population in Bangladesh.

Now, it is very clear that the Prime Minister Sheikh Hasina and Awami League Government of Bangladesh cheated with the Chittagong Hill Tracts Buddhists population by the peace accord, whereas about a million rehabilitated Muslim population in the Chittagong Hill Tracts regions received a set of free and secure living conditions and increased their Muslim population by ever secured reproductive family planning, working to spread Islam and destroy Buddhism where all the works are conducted by the sponsor of the Bangladesh Government. However, rehabilitated people still have connections with their origin addresses from where they came in the Chittagong Hill Tracts region, so it is still possible to withdraw them from the Chittagong Hill Tracts region and send them back to their native locations. However, after a generation, they will be fully disconnected from their origin, and to withdraw them would not be possible. So, to the Chittagong Hill Tracts Regional Government of the tribal, indigenous, micronations, and freedom fighters through the Chittagong Hill Tracts Peace Accord 1997 was the last yet official initiative of the Chittagong Peace Process was a big deception by Sheikh Hasina & AL-GOB. Bangladesh made the Buddhists freedom fighters unarmed by taking deposits of all arms and weapons and did not yet implement the signed peace agreement, but also made more rightful free access to the Muslim people to Islamize there everywhere by perishing Buddhists people. However, the purpose of all deals was to establish the Independence and Autonomy Government of a Parbatya Commonwealth, the formation of legislative assembly houses, and parliamentary building construction.

Over the years, several emails, press releases, and messages/information/queries were sent to many first authorities of the Bangladeshi government, including the Prime Minister's Office, but nobody spoke about it. Prime Minister Sheikh Hasina and Awami League Government of Bangladesh took the last official initiative of the Chittagong Peace Process by conducting and signing the CHT Peace Accord 1997, but now AL-GOB again in the government power and Sheikh Hasina is also Prime Minister since 2009, and they have not yet implemented the peace agreement's major treaties. In addition to the historical and legal background, the General Hari Seldon Private Commission Resolution Act was introduced in the Parbatya Commonwealth Act for Independence of Autonomy Government, formation of legislative assembly houses, and parliamentary building construction.

Bangladesh also became a member of the Chinese Belt and Road Initiative, whereas China also provided Age's best significant development support to Bangladesh. Therefore, it is a very relevant, important, and urgent issue to allow China as the head of the international government organization One Belt and One Road Initiative, whereas Chinese rules and regulations may be partially applicable in Bangladesh to provide support to the Chittagong Peace Process, including adaptation of the developed legislative issues for the people of Parbatya nation's ownership which very seriously violated and was fallen very badly. Therefore, the rising peace may not be possible aslong Bangladesh armed forces and government are having presence/access in the Chittagong Hill Tracts region but Parbatya one region autonomy of special administration or sovereignty by the two-state solution. Otherwise, there should be no reason to survive the world's largest indigenous population group/nation state of Parbatya CHT in a single place in the coming decades.

However, the Global War on Terrorism, which again may be called the World War on Global Terrorism, is actually the third world war, whereas Russia also joined the World War against the NATO-Ukraine alliance's intention of the operation searchlight of finding Islamic terrorism forms in the Independent Nation states, especially the commonwealth leader of the Russian Federation. On the other hand, Myanmar also intends to attack Bangladesh on the same issues if Islamic terrorism threatens the Union of Myanmar and religious Buddhists' population freedom and rights of autonomous Regional Government establishment through the implementation of the CHT Peace Accord 1997, which has not yet been enforced from 1997 to 2023.

Domestic Situation Review

The Chittagong Hill Tracts Peace Accord 1997 established an independent "Regional Council" for the Indigenous people, which was meant to serve as the supreme sovereign body/authority or a major organ for the state government system in relation to certain matters. Later, it is assumed that the meaning of the word "Council" has tried to change the meaning of other words such as mass-gathering, meeting/seminar, conference, etc., that is, annual conferences or annual councils, which have been introduced to exercising/practices among civil societies, political parties, and various nationwide activities. It fully misguided to the purpose of the deal and attempted to make the CHT Peace Accord 1997 meaningless and to perish all its historical and legal components to be unclaimable by making the Buddhists' indigenous

tribes ethnic people disappear from the Parbatya Chittagong Hill Tracts Region.

For example, Congress is a legislature of the federal government of the United States, which is composed of two houses: The Senate floor(s) and the House of Representatives. However, in the Bharat and British-Indian sub-continental regions in Asia, Congress is known as a political party, the Congress Party, or simply "Congress", which was founded by Allan Octavian Hume (Wikipedia: Indian National Congress). Furthermore, the term "Congress" is also used for the meaning of mass gatherings of the people like meeting/seminar, conference i.e. annual conference or annual congress. As also The European Council is a collegiate body of the European Union, among the 3 supreme institutions, alongwith 2 others i.e. The European Commission is an executive body and The European Parliament is a legislative body of the European Union.

However, the Chittagong Hill Tracts Peace Accord 1997 in the course of the Parbatya separation movement and war-fighting battles was a historical legal agreement for independence of the autonomy government, formation of legislative assembly house, and parliament building construction, towards a commonwealth state of the Parbatya's kingdoms, which (was) led by three kings, also called the Chief of the Chakma Circle (called chakma people), Chief of the Marma Circle (also called bohmong people), and the Chief of the Mong Circle (actually marma people). Marma people from the Mong and Bohmong circles also called Moghs wheres they established 2 separate circles: Marma/Bohmong and Mong (Wikipedia: Tribal Monarchy in the Chittagong Hill Tracts, Chakma Circle, Bohmong Circle, Mong Circle). The Bangladesh government doesn't acknowledge their kingship or royal government system(s) as still declining autonomy/sovereignty of Parbatya, even signed regional government deals yet not been permitted but somehow un/officially uses the term chieftdom, chieftain, etc.

General Hari Seldon Private Commission Resolution Act, 2023

The purpose of the General Hari Seldon Private Commission is to establish a Permanent Resolution Act in Parbatya Commonwealth Act for Independence of Autonomy Government, Formation of Legislative Assembly Houses and Parliament Building Construction.

Article#1

Title: Parbatya Commonwealth Act for Independence of Autonomy Government, Formation of Legislative Assembly House and Parliament Building Construction.

Article#2

The current status of The Parbatya Chattagram Hill Tracts Region in Bangladesh are as follows:

1. People's Republic Bangladesh Government's Administrative Districts Territory of the Chittagong Hill Tracts Region of the Chittagong Administration Division of Government of Bangladesh;
2. Chittagong Hill Tracts Airspace Surveillance Wing of the Chittagong Major Command of Bangladesh Air Force;
3. Chittagong Hill Tracts Mountain Division of the Training Command of the Bangladesh Army;

4. Chittagong Hill Tracts Commodore Commanding Schedules of the Chittagong Fleet Command of Bangladesh Navy.

Article#3

Factors of the Parbatya Commonwealth Act for Independence of Autonomy Government, Formation of Legislative Assembly House and Parliament Building Construction:

1. Thousands of years ancient's indigenous people in the Parbatya Chattagram Hill Tracts districts regional state in Bangladesh have become tribal nation after gradually separation from the Buddha Edge Rule, Hindustan Mahabharat Bers, Commonwealth Realms of the British Empire, and Separation of under Bangladesh from Pakistan at the End.
2. Buddhism believer tribal nations who are the vast majority population in the Parbatya state have been fighting for independence for several decades.
3. After formation of Bangladesh, the Parbatya state became part of the Bangladesh as Parbatya Chittagong Hill Tracts which was divided into three districts and furthermore others administrative division as per Bangladesh Government System.
4. The Bangladesh Government also deputed large numbers of military resources like military personnel, arms & weapons, vehicles and built military bases & infrastructure which are mostly used as the training purpose of the Bangladesh Armed Forces in the Chittagong Hill Tracts districts.
5. The Bangladesh government officially rehabilitated about a million of Muslim Bengali people here as auxiliary civil defense support forces who came to Parbatya from all other districts of Bangladesh under Bengali Rehabilitation in Chittagong Hill Tracts Districts Project.
6. Chittagong Hill Tracts region is also part of the British Commonwealth of Nations of the United Kingdom Royal Realms.
7. Few official Christian missions in very limited capacity are also active and work in Parbatya state.
8. The United Nations opened a permanent mission office in Parbatya.
9. The Parbatya has a set of religious channels of communications with Religion of Buddhism dominant including relevant folks' belief/buddhist countries & regions i.e. Bhutan, Myanmar, Cambodia, China, Hong Kong, Japan, Tibet, Laos, Macau, Mongolia, Singapore, Sri Lanka, Taiwan, Thailand, Kalmykia, Vietnam; including large Buddhist people living in North Korea, Nepal, India and South Korea.
10. No other major foreign missions are activated here i.e. India, America, Russia, Europe, Arab, Israel.
11. The Parbatya state currently functions under Bangladesh.
12. Parbatya having world recognized an indigenous royal government system lead by Devasish Roy an indigenous King was born & raised in the Chakma tribal circle, is one of three tribes in the Chittagong Hill Tracts districts along with Chakma Tribe, Marma Tribe and Mong Tribe whereas furthermore they are divided into other sub-tribal circles and having different names.
13. The people of the three circle tribes Chakma, Marma and Mong are living in the Rangamati, Bandarban and Khagrachari districts in the Chittagong Hill Tracts region in Bangladesh.

14. In other words, the State of Parbatya may be called the Parbatya Kingdom.
15. Parbatya has different political organizations, committees, activities and parties.
16. United People's Party is most known, currently led by Shantu Larma who was also Commanding General of the Parbatya Peace Corps who contributed to establish Chittagong Hill Tracts Treaty with the Bangladesh Government in 1997 which is yet last officially signed activity of Chittagong Hill Tracts Peace Process. But the Peace Accord orders were not implemented until this day of 2023. The peace force ended the war and submitted their arms & weapons to the Bangladesh Government in response to the committed deals of the peace accord in order to recognize their autonomous regional government.

Article#4

The Chittagong Hill Tracts Peace Accord allowed the indigenous tribal status identified/known people of the Chittagong Hill Tracts Region to form an autonomous regional free fair independent government and approved the order to withdraw all military power & resources from Chittagong Hill Tracts which were deployed by Bangladesh.

Following major recognitions stated under the Parbatya Commonwealth Act for Independence of Autonomy Government, Formation of Legislative Assembly House and Parliament Building Construction:

1. The Royal Government of Parbatya Kingdom will continue to perform as independent national government of Parbatya;
2. Recognizes political party(s) and the political government;
3. The Government System will establish Legislative Assembly House(s) who will create a constitution;
4. The government will collect funds from any source that can be helpful/useful for them by giving money to construct a parliament building.

Article#5

Nation: The people in the Parbatya are the world's largest indigenous population group living in a single place who were identified as tribal. The act also recognized the people's rights to express themselves as a nation and the right to continue the international consultation to get recognition as a sovereign country to preserve and uphold their all indigenous and/or tribute/tribal rights of culture & practice, language & education/learning, belief & religion and each & every components of the nationality with a flag government system including nation's armed defense and diplomatic missions in abroad.

Conclusion

The United States of America didn't state any expression of interest on the Chittagong Peace Process towards the Chittagong Hill Tracts separation movement for autonomy or sovereignty of the Parbatya, Chittagong Hill Tracts conflict and the Chittagong Hill Tracts Peace Accord 1997. But the United States looks for America's priority theater basis: contributory participation to protect rights of the needy, ensure human rights, conflict resolution for maintaining peace, Indo-Pacific regional stability, global security, upholding democratic mission of sovereign land and expanding opportunities of the continuing development of humanity.

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⁵Speaker, Royal House of Angeles, Sovereign Order of Royal El-Romania.

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Statement of the Data

This situation review article has been written mainly based on the previous memory and personal observation which I learned from time to time by watching television news, listening to radio broadcasts, reading printed newspapers & online news websites, articles from various sources and also physically traveled the entire Parbatya region. In this capacity, I wrote a few blog posts and social media posts, especially on Facebook and X (Twitter), and also wrote a few messages, notes, and articles on this topic, which were delivered to more than 300 journalists in most of all news media in Bangladesh and approximately 200 people of the international community around the world. Finally, a synopsis of the complete/overview information was published in the GitHub post and its DataCommit section, and Asgardia Space Nation's website. To the best of my knowledge, the provided information is accurate, and the article does not have conflicts of interest unless the provided (accurate) information may conflict with any group of people.

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